

A series of decorative blue bars in various shades and widths, including a long dark blue bar at the top, a white horizontal line, and several vertical bars of varying heights and widths in different shades of blue.

Report on focus group discussion and survey results on the role of libraries during crises

Implementation Country: Greece

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Date: May 2025

Co-funded by
the European Union

Deliverable Factsheet

Project Number:	2024-1-EE01-KA220-HED-000243324
Project Acronym:	CAELUM
Project Title:	Open science supporting vulnerable communities: empowering university libraries in crisis response
Title of Document:	Report on focus group discussion and survey results on the role of libraries during crises
Output:	WP2A2
Due date according to contact:	30/06/2025
Editor(s):	Web2Learn
Contributor(s):	Korina Defteraïou, Katerina Zourou
Reviewer(s):	10/6/2025
Approved by:	University of Tartu
Abstract:	This report summarises and discusses the findings and the insights of the focus group discussion and the survey results that point out diverse perspectives on library roles in crises.
Keyword list:	Focus group discussion, survey replies, libraries role, crisis, perspectives
Copyright	Creative Commons License 4.0 International
Please cite as	Defteraïou, K., Zourou, K., (2025). Report on focus group discussion and survey results on the role of libraries during crises. CAELUM consortium.

Partnership

	Name	Logo
1	University of Tartu	
2	Web2Learn	
3	Kaunas University of Technology	
4	Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies	
5	SKS Knowledge Services	

Revision History

Version	Date	Revised by	Reason
V0.1	29/05/2025	Stefania Oikonomou	Internal review

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Disclaimer:

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List of Abbreviations

The following table presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviations	Description
European Union	EU
Higher Education	HE
Research Question	RQ
Ukraine	UA
Work Package	WP

Executive Summary

This report summarises and discusses the findings and insights of the focus group discussion and the survey results in Greece, pointing out diverse perspectives on library roles in crises. In this framework, the collected data from the focus group discussion and the survey are grouped thematically based on the research questions (RQs). The report describes the methodology of the focus group discussion and the survey and presents the key findings. Afterwards, it gives prominence to practices, challenges, and opportunities for civic engagement through university libraries, that emerge from the results of the focus group discussion and the survey replies.

The report concludes with recommendations of possible actions that could help libraries undertake a central role in communities during different types of crises. The overall aim of this report is to present firsthand perspectives from academic staff, students, and library personnel, thus enriching the project's knowledge base.

About CAELUM

CAELUM (Open science supporting vulnerable communities: empowering university libraries in crisis response, 2025-2027, <https://caelum.ut.ee/>) is a 2-year Erasmus+ project that places university libraries in the forefront of crisis response through open science, supporting vulnerable communities and bolstering EU-UA cooperation. Through a series of activities, CAELUM aims to upskill university libraries' staff in innovative and interdisciplinary approaches to crisis response and promote and sustain university libraries-driven open knowledge and civic engagement among HE students and staff for crisis response. Thus, CAELUM empowers university libraries in leveraging open and citizen science approaches as well as community engagement practices for crisis response in multiple contexts.

1. Context

This report is the deliverable of the activity 2 of the Work Package 2 (WP2) that aims to offer firsthand perspectives regarding the role of libraries in crises. The research methods that have been selected for collecting data from the target audience are:

- a focus group discussion
- a survey

The results of the focus group discussion in Greece offer insights that explore participants' experiences, expectations, and reflections on the role of libraries in crises, while the survey replies help us understand what kind of support people expect from libraries in crises, and what opportunities exist for libraries to help build more resilient, informed, and connected communities. The combination of these two research methods offers qualitative and quantitative data that allows us to explore further the perceived role of libraries during crises and help us to identify current trends and patterns that will be further analysed below.

1.1. Research questions

This report analyses the findings of the focus group discussion and the survey targeting mainly the following groups: academic staff, students, and library personnel. The research questions are common in both methods and have been decided at consortium's level as per below:

- RQ1: What has been the libraries' role during crises?
- RQ2: What are the expectations and perceived needs of students, academic staff, library professionals (and others) regarding library support in crisis situations?
- RQ3: What barriers and gaps have university libraries faced in responding to crises?
- RQ4: How can university libraries contribute to public engagement and community resilience during and after crises?

In the framework of WP3 (activity 2), CAELUM partners will implement case studies that involve the practical application of the CAELUM methodology in real-world scenarios. Each partner will undertake a unique case study, addressing diverse crises. Web2Learn

has decided to implement a case study that addresses the needs of disabled citizens through combined institutional and community-led initiatives in the context of an academic library. As a result, Web2Learn has added a research question that is relevant to this case study and is the following:

→ RQ5: How can libraries ensure inclusivity and accessibility to their services?

The collection of data in this field will allow us to have first insights at national level about the accessibility of libraries resources and services to disabled users and will prepare the transition to the specific case study that will unfold at national level.

Last but not least, this report follows on from a desk research that has resulted in a comprehensive resource collection exploring how university libraries respond to crises at international, European and national level and is available at the CAELUM website [here](#).

1.2 Demographics

The target audience for the focus group discussion and the survey was academic staff, students, and library personnel but also members of the wider community that are somehow connected to libraries and education (for example school educators).

Below is a figure that depicts that the majority of the participants (71%) in the focus group discussion was library staff.

1. Figure: Current role of the participants in the focus group discussion

The same applies for the participants in the survey as depicted in the second figure below (almost 77% of the replies come from library staff).

2. What is your current role within the academic community? (Select the one you identify with the most)

26 responses

2. Figure: Current role of the participants in the survey

2. Methodology

A. Focus group discussion

The focus group discussion took place online on Friday, May 16th 2025 with the involvement of 7 external participants and 3 staff personnel from Web2Learn. The discussion was conducted through the Zoom platform in the form of a 60-minute semi-structured discussion in Greek. The current professional status of the participants is: library personnel (5), academic staff (1) and a cleric-teacher of secondary education (1). One of the participants was blind. Beyond the corpus of the questions that was agreed at consortium level, Web2Learn added 3 questions related to disability as it is the theme of the case study that we will implement in WP3, as already mentioned. The majority of the questions were answered from by least 2 persons orally during the online discussion, while 4 questions were answered by all participants in writing with the use of an online whiteboard (<https://excalidraw.com/>) where all participants wrote their thoughts and/or opinions in bullet points. The discussion was recorded and we took notes with the answers of the participants. The answers were then processed and grouped thematically. The questions that were discussed during the focus group discussion are available in English in Annex I.

B. Survey

The survey was anonymous and it took 7-10 minutes to respond. The tool that was used for the development and the distribution of the online survey was Google form. It was shared in Greek, at national level, to the following target audience: academic staff, students, library personnel and wider audiences related to education. It was available to the public from May 1st to May 31. Overall, we received 27 responses. The questions of the survey are available in English in Annex II.

3. Key findings

The key findings of the focus group discussion and the survey replies have been grouped thematically and are analysed hereafter. The themes below result from the key research questions that are common to the discussion and survey and have been agreed at consortium level. This match between the research questions and the thematic analysis is depicted in the following figure.

3. Figure: Match between RQs and thematic analysis of findings

Moreover, the consortium has agreed that each partner may supplement these main research questions, with some case-specific questions relevant to the case study that each partner will implement in WP3 during the pilot projects. Web2Learn will

implement a case study that addresses the needs of disabled users through combined institutional and community-led initiatives in libraries. Thus, Web2Learn has added an extra research question that is the following:

- RQ5: How can libraries ensure inclusivity and accessibility to their services?
→ matched with theme V

After the analysis of the findings relevant to each theme, there is a figure that synthesises the keywords of each theme replies in the form of a mind map (Figure 4, 5, 7, 9, 10).

3.1. Theme I: Library roles during crises

Participants both in the focus group discussion and the survey overwhelmingly perceive a wider role of libraries than just providers of academic resources and books. 50% of the participants in the survey replied that they have received some kind of support (such as practical help, information, or emotional support) from a library during crises. Both in the focus group discussion and the survey replies, participants underscored the central role that libraries can undertake in periods of crises as trustworthy institutions. During any kind of crisis, while uncertainty and doubt prevails, the libraries are considered as trusted institutions in the wider community as the librarians have been trained to provide reliable information and services to the public. On the other hand, in academia, it was underscored during the focus group discussion that the trust of the newcomer students in the Higher Education (HE) is not taken for granted but it should be built incrementally as many of them have never used any library in the past. Moreover, many participants both in the discussion and the survey (84%) underscored the importance of the technological means used by the libraries, such as remote access tools or accessible digital resources for disabled users, especially when physical access to the library is not possible due to disability issues or external political, social, health or environmental crises. Some participants referred to the emergency services that they have received from libraries during a crisis, such as provision of masks or personal protective equipment (PPE).

4. Figure: Mind map of library roles during crises

3.2. Theme II: Expectations and needs

The majority of the participants in the survey (84%) replied that in a crisis situation, they would expect from a library online services (ebooks, databases, etc.). Physical space for study/work, access to accurate information and Internet or Wi-Fi are also highly expected with 65%, 61% and 61% in survey replies respectively. The access to accurate information during a crisis was also highly underscored during the focus group discussion. The below expectations and needs of students, academic staff, library professionals and general public regarding library support in crisis situations were common in the discussion and the survey:

- direct communication with helpful and friendly library personnel;
- connection with other members of the community;
- safe physical space for calm and privacy;
- spiritual guidance for mental health and wellbeing;

5. Figure: Mind map for expectations and needs from a library during a crisis

3.3. Theme III: Barriers and support gaps

According to the survey replies, the main barriers that would prevent a patron to use the library during a crisis are:

- the library is closed (85% in survey replies)
- the library has no internet access (57%)
- difficult to find up-to-date information from the library website and social media channels (42%)

It is encouraging that 84% of the respondents in the survey replied that they would feel comfortable approaching a library for help in a crisis as presented in the following figure.

10. Would you feel comfortable approaching a library for help in a crisis?
(select one option)

6. Figure: Would you feel comfortable approaching a library for help in crisis?

However, a gap that has been mentioned both in the survey replies and also in the focus group discussion is that the libraries in Greece, due to low funding, do not always have the possibility to promote their work to the wider community and this leads to a general lack of knowledge about library services among potential users. As a result, in a period of crisis, users usually lack the knowledge of the services that the libraries could provide as they have no previous experience in libraries. Another gap that was discussed mainly in the focus group discussion was the lack of will or expertise by the library staff to respond to a crisis and the lack of full accessibility for disabled users, esp. in resources related to culture.

7. Figure: Mind map for barriers and support gaps

3.4. Theme IV: Public engagement and community support

During the focus group discussion, the participants discussed various actions that the libraries could develop as a way to contribute to public engagement and community support in times of crises. Below are some ideas discussed:

- Organisation of activities, events etc for the public
- Collaboration with other libraries, university services and academic staff
- Presentation of the library services to the courses during the 1st year of bachelor studies
- Learning by previous experience
- Training of library staff to engage students in libraries and to manage crises
- Volunteering groups that create accessible material for their co-students with visual impairment

As far as the survey replies are concerned, the majority of respondents (65%) stated that they have participated in community-focused events or activities at their university library as depicted in the following figure.

12. Have you ever participated in any community-focused events or activities at your university library? (Select one option)

26 responses

8. Figure: Have you ever participated in any community-focused events or activities at your university library?

Moreover, participants in both cases stated that staff upskilling for proactive crisis management, cultural and social activities for community building, job search help, and educational programs would be very important in public engagement.

9. Figure: Mind map for public engagement in crises

3.5. Theme V: Inclusivity and accessibility to library resources and services

The issue of accessibility to library resources and services seems to be a thorny issue for libraries. In the focus group discussion, the participants shared that libraries most of the time are physically accessible to users with mobility problems and may have working stations adjusted to the needs of users with visual or hearing impairment but it is not always easy for users with disability to reach the library and the working stations. Although the academic libraries in Greece have created some common rules for the creation of accessible digital material in a common repository for disabled users with visual impairment (available [here](#)), the transformation of digital resources to accessible ones is an ongoing procedure that requires permanent funding and human resources. The role of technology was a common subject both in the focus group discussion and the survey as the technological equipment used for disabled users should be updated every 6-10 years and the libraries lack permanent funding resources for this cause. Finally, in both cases, the importance of the training of the library staff regarding the needs of the disabled users (including users with learning difficulties and mental health problems) and the use of technological tools (assistive technology software) was underscored as a core element in transforming the libraries to more accessible places.

10. Figure: Mind map for accessibility and inclusivity in libraries.

4. Reflections on practices, challenges and opportunities

The key findings of the focus group discussion and the survey replies analysed above point out some key practices that libraries engage during crises, common challenges that exist for libraries but also opportunities that arise for upscaling their role in the community before, during and after a crisis.

4.1. Practices

Libraries bring a variety of practices to serve and support their communities during different kinds of crises. Some key practices identified are listed below:

- Dissemination of accurate information about the crisis.
- Organisation of events that facilitate social networking and build community resilience.
- Spiritual guidance.
- Provision of remote services and training activities when access to the physical space is not possible.
- Provision of digital resources for disabled users.
- Collaboration with other libraries, university's services and academic staff for crisis management.
- Outreach activities that aim to approach the less engaged users (ex. presentation of library services to newcomers in HE).
- Continuous training for library staff for proactive management of possible crises.
- Organisation of volunteering groups for crisis management or for facilitation of disabled users.

4.2. Challenges

Beyond their traditional role as knowledge institutions that lend books and offer access to resources, libraries should adapt their role to socioeconomic, environmental and political context, especially in periods of uncertainty and doubt. The findings analysed above (especially in Theme III: Barriers and support gaps) refer to a number of challenges that libraries face in supporting the community during diverse crises. The main challenges are listed below:

- Lack of permanent funding
- Lack of sufficient human resources
- Lack of will or expertise by the library staff to respond to a crisis
- No previous experience in academic libraries for newcomers
- Limited accessibility for disabled users
- Restricted knowledge about the libraries and the provided services

4.3. Opportunities

Despite the challenges listed above, a crisis may also create an opportunity for libraries to review their traditional role and transform into community support and resilience hubs as the results of the focus group discussion and the survey have indicated. Based on the findings, libraries are widely considered trustworthy institutions in the community and this is crucial in a period of crisis during which uncertainty and doubt prevails. Participants in the discussion but also survey respondents highlighted that they would approach a library for help during a crisis and this is an encouraging finding that libraries should take into account and invest in emergency preparedness. Thus, the libraries could illuminate their role as resilience hubs and raise public awareness of their roles, especially during crises.

5. Conclusion: lessons and possible actions

Summing up, we would like to underscore some main points that arise from both the focus group discussion and the survey: the respondents highlighted that, expect for libraries' role in ensuring access to accurate information and Internet access in a crisis situation, staff training and empathy are just as critical as infrastructures. A central challenge that Greek libraries face is limited funding and human resources, limitations that also affect the services and resources provided to disabled users. Although libraries are considered trustworthy institutions, their impact is often undervalued or unknown to the wider community. Hence, it is important for libraries to become more visible and vocal about their services and serve proactively during crises, not just reactively.

In summary, while libraries face notable challenges during crises, they also have significant opportunities to reinforce their positions as vital community hubs. This can be achieved by addressing funding and staffing issues, enhancing staff training, and promoting their social mission in communities through outreach activities and collaborative efforts with other relevant institutions, thus enhancing their role as pillars of social support and resilience, especially in times of emergency.

ANNEX I

Focus group discussion questions

I Experience with Crisis Contexts

What kinds of crises have you experienced or thought about?

How have these situations affected your research or personal life?

Where would you turn first for help in a crisis, and why?

II Library Roles During Crises

Do you consider libraries as trusted institutions in your community? Why or why not?

Have you ever received help or support from a library during a crisis?

How did the library respond (or could have responded) to the crisis during that time?

III Expectations and Needs

If such a crisis occurred tomorrow, what kind of support would be most important to you?

What would you expect from your library in this situation?

IV Barriers and Gaps

What are the main barriers that prevent libraries from supporting people in this specific crisis?

Are there reasons why you or others might not seek help from a library? If yes, how could we change it?

V Public Engagement & Community Resilience

Can you imagine a library being a place for community action or support? If yes, then how?

In your opinion, how can libraries build stronger communities during or after a crisis?

CASE SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

Report on focus group discussion and
survey results on the role of libraries during
crises

1. Are the libraries that you visit/work physically accessible to disabled students and/or citizens?
2. Have you ever participated in any library activities that also involved disabled students and/or citizens?
3. Are the physical and digital resources of the library that you work/visit available to disabled persons? If yes, in which way?

ANNEX II

Survey questions

I Background information

1. Age *(select one option)*

18-25

26-35

36-45

46-60

61+

Prefer not to say

2. What is your current role within the academic community? *(Select the one you identify with the most)*

Student

Academic staff (e.g. lecturer, researcher)

Library staff

Administrative or support staff

Citizen scientist

I am not a member of the academic community

Other: _____

3. What type of crisis has affected you the most? *(Select one option)*

War or armed conflict

Political turbulence

Pandemic or health crisis

- Mental health or well-being challenges in academic life
- Information overload and challenges related to open science in research
- Climate related crisis (e.g. heatwave, drought, flooding)
- Disinformation during emergencies (e.g. war, disasters)
- Problems with social integration or job opportunities for international students
- Barriers faced by disabled people (e.g. access, inclusion)
- Other: _____

4. How do you usually find information during a crisis? *(Select all that apply)*

- Social media
- News media
- Government websites
- University websites or communication
- Friends/family
- Library channels
- Academic journals or research sources
- Other: _____

II Library Roles During Crises

5. Have you ever received support from a library during a crisis? Support could include practical help, information, or emotional support. *(Select one option)*

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

5a. If yes, what kind of support did you receive?
Open question

6. In a crisis situation, which forms of support would you expect or seek from a library?

(Select all that apply)

Access to curated information

Internet or Wi-Fi

Charging stations

Physical space for study/work

Mental health support or safe environment

Cultural events and social interaction

Help with government forms or aid

Help with job seeking or employment support

Emergency supplies (masks, flashlights, etc.)

Online library services (ebooks, databases, etc.)

Guidance for using academic databases

Training sessions and courses

Support for research or community projects that respond to the crisis

I wouldn't expect anything from a library

Other: _____

III Expectations and Needs

7. When facing a crisis, how important would each of the following be for you personally?

Some of these needs may be supported by libraries, others may not. Please rate how important each would be to you personally in a crisis. (Rate each from "Not at all important" to "Very important")

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important
Access to credible, accurate, and curated information					

Reliable internet access					
Access to physical space or shelter					
Community connection					
Support for mental health					
Online library access					
Emergency information updates					
Assistance with digital tools					
Being part of the solution					
Opportunities for collaboration or problem-solving with others					
Feeling informed and involved					

7. What would make a library feel like a supportive and safe space during a crisis (e.g., space, staff, resources)?

Open question

IV Barriers and Support Gaps

8. What might prevent you from using library services in a crisis? (Select all that apply)

Library is closed

Difficult to find up-to-date information from the library website and social media channels

Library location is hard to reach

Library is not accessible or inclusive for disabled users

Library has no internet access

Didn't know library could help

Negative past experiences at the library

Lack of trust in libraries

Other: _____

9. Would you feel comfortable approaching a library for help in crisis? (select one option)

Yes

No

Not sure

9a. If you answered "No" or "Not sure," please explain why:

Open question

V Public Engagement and Community Support

10. Do you agree with the following statement: Libraries can play a meaningful role in supporting communities during crises.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

11. Have you ever participated in any community-focused events or activities at your university library? (Select one option)

Yes

No

Not sure

11a. If yes, what kind of activity or event was it?

Open question

12. What activities or services could a library offer to support your community in difficult times?

Open question

13. How can libraries ensure inclusivity and accessibility to their services?

Open question (case specific)

14. Do you have anything to add?

Open question